

Admission time deep swab specimens compared to surgical bone sampling in hospitalised individuals with diabetic foot osteomyelitis and soft tissue infection.

A Manas¹, S Taori², R Ahluwalia³ H Slim⁴ C Manu¹ H Rashid⁴ V Kavarthapu³ M Edmonds¹ P Vas^{1,5}

¹ Diabetic Foot Clinic

² Microbiology

³ Orthopaedic Surgery

⁴ Vascular Surgery

King's College Hospital, United Kingdom.

⁵ Institute of Diabetes, Endocrinology and Obesity, King's Health Partners, London.

Abstract

Aim: Our study aimed to evaluate if deep swab cultures taken at time-point of a hospital admission with a severe diabetic foot infection could reliably identify pathogens compared to cultured bone specimens in a distinct group of patients admitted to hospital with acute exacerbation of diabetic foot osteomyelitis.

Method: Retrospective review of consecutive hospital admissions with a severely infected diabetic foot, Texas Grade 3 ulceration and clinico-radiological evidence of osteomyelitis over a 9-month period. A deep swab (DWS) through the actively infected discharging ulcer down to the bone, was taken at time of admission. Bone sampling was undertaken during surgery (SBS). The number of organisms isolated per individual per sampling technique was then determined and data is represented as such.

Results: A total of 63 subjects (age 60.8 ± 13.5 years, 75% male, 80% Type 2 diabetes, HbA1C $8.9\% \pm 2.2\%$) met the inclusion criteria. The proportion of gram-positive (DWS 49% v SBS 52%) and gram-negative (DWS 60% v SBS 60%) isolates was similar between the techniques. However, the overall ordnance of the isolates between the two techniques was only fair ($\kappa=0.302$). The best concordance was observed for *Staphylococcus aureus* ($\kappa=0.571$) and MRSA ($\kappa=0.644$). There was a correlation between number of isolates in SBS with prior antibiotic therapy of any duration ($r= -0.358$, $p=0.005$) and with the duration of ulceration ($r=0.296$, $p=0.045$); no clinical corelated were found for DWS. Prior antibiotic therapy ($p=0.03$) and duration of ulceration <8 weeks ($p=0.025$) were predictive of negative growth on SBS.

Conclusion:

Introduction

Diabetic foot ulceration (DFU) is often complicated by infection. It is estimated that 40% - 80% of all DFU develop an infection at some time point with a negative impact on clinical outcomes (1). Importantly, up to 15%-60% of all infected DFU go on to develop diabetic foot osteomyelitis (DFO) (2). Culture specific antibiotic therapy is of crucial importance in all diabetic foot infections and international guidelines recommend appropriate, reliable sampling techniques to determine the causative pathogen (3). From a clinical standpoint, such an evaluation is frequently challenging given the non-linear clinical course, existence of complex clinical phenotypes and the consequent in ensuring the correct sampling techniques are employed. These important factors will impact on how clinicians will interpret and react to the results (4). These challenges are exponentially compounded in the chronic, non-healing DFU, where there is constant evolution of the microbial flora (5).

One important group of patients are those with a known DFU, already receiving outpatient-based care and subsequently hospitalised with a severe limb threatening infective episode. Among these, of particular concern is the specific clinical phenotype with clinically identifiable osteomyelitis, who are at increased risk of suboptimal outcomes including prolonged hospitalisation, an extended wound healing period, development of recalcitrant osteomyelitis and potentially, lower limb amputation (6, 7). Many such individuals would have already received prior antibiotic therapy in a clinic setting as an initial strategy to contain milder forms of infection. The challenge in managing such individuals is the lack of reliable microbiological information at the point of admission to guide targeted antibiotic therapy. While surgical debridement of all infected tissue including bone is the favoured method of achieving infection control, delays in surgical planning are often encountered because of concerns about fitness for surgery, need for preoperative optimisation and diabetic foot patients are, at times, indecisive about such surgery. Hence, the lack of clear microbiological perspective will delay the early institution of culture-guided antibiotic therapy and increase the reliance on broad spectrum empirical antibiotics because of a lack of clear right microbiological perspective.

Studies have indicated that results obtained from swab cultures, even from deep sinus tracts, are unreliable (3, 8). However, this assumption is based on data from superficial swabbing (9), retrospective cohort analysis, a mixed case-load of inpatient and outpatient subjects (9-11) and non-selective patients groups with widely heterogeneous (variant) ulcer stages without distinction of clinical phenotypes (9, 12) amongst others. Diabetes foot guidelines, therefore, recommend the use of tissue specimens in soft tissue infections, and bone sampling as optimal when DFO is suspected (13, 14). It is important to note that many studies on microbiological assessment techniques have excluded patients with antecedent or current antibiotic usage, creating a paucity of knowledge in this particular area (9, 10, 12, 15, 16) and limiting the generalizability of the findings, in particular, to the acutely infected hospitalised group. We therefore aimed to evaluate if carefully taken deep swab cultures, taken through infective tracts at time of hospital admission with a severe limb threatening infection, could provide reliable information compared to bone culture from operating theatre specimens, irrespective of previous antibiotic treatment status, in a group with clinico-radiological evidence of acute (or acute on chronic) osteomyelitis. At our centre, this constitutes the largest cohort of individuals requiring hospitalisation.

Patients and methods

Patients

Retrospective study of consecutive diabetic foot patients who were admitted to King's College Hospital over a 12-month period – January to December 2014. All the patients were admitted with an infective exacerbation of a previously known DFU. A clinical diagnosis of DFO was established by a combination of probe to bone test (100% present) and typical radiological abnormalities on plain radiography and/or magnetic resonance imaging (100% abnormal) (17). Thus, all patients included in the analysis had DFO with severe soft tissue infection (Texas 3b) or additionally, ischaemia (Texas 3d). Neuropathy was defined as a vibration perception threshold >25 Volts measured using a Neurothesiometer (Horwell Scientific, Nottingham, UK). Ischaemia was defined as the presence of monophasic pulsation at the dorsalis pedis artery or the inframalleolar posterior tibial artery on

Doppler waveform analysis as minimum [9]. Chronic DFU was defined as ulceration with a duration of greater than 8 weeks and past antibiotic treatment was considered as 'long term' if used for longer than 4 weeks consecutively leading up to the admission.

Specimen collection

On admission, deep wound swabbing (DWS) was performed in each patient after ulcer cleaning with sterile gauze soaked in sterile saline and after removal of superficial slough layer by sharp debridement. Swabs were obtained through the ulcer base and tracts by vigorous rotation of the swab, contacting the bone when possible and held in contact with the wound bed for 4-5 seconds. Surgical bone specimens (SBS) were obtained intra-operatively, under sterile conditions, after debridement of all infected tissue.

DWS were cultured on blood agar (aerobic and anaerobic) and MacConkeys agar (with Tazobactam+Piperacillin disc, an in-house adaptation to screen for resistant Gram-negative bacteria). *Staphylococcus aureus* and beta- haemolytic streptococci were identified to species level with full sensitivities, Gram-negative bacteria were reported as a group except if resistant to Tazobactam+Piperacillin, in which case they were identified to species level and reported with full sensitivities. Anaerobes were reported as a group. Coagulase negative *Staphylococci*, diphtheroids and faecal *Streptococci* were reported. SBS were cultured as above but with the addition of Robertsons cooked meat medium inoculation and incubated for 48 hours followed by subculture onto chocolate agar and fastidious anaerobe agar. All growth from bone biopsies was identified to species level with full sensitivities.

Statistical analysis

All samples relate to a single event – an episode where the swab was taken and the index surgery where bone sampling was undertaken. Therefore, the results are described on a per patient basis. Quantitative variables are shown as mean with standard deviation. Qualitative variables are shown as percentage (%). Comparison of quantitative variables was performed with Mann-Whitney U test and comparison of proportions was performed with Chi-square test. The statistical significance level was

set at $p < 0.05$. Percentage of instances in which bone and deep swab samples yielded the same pathogen for a given patient was assessed. Kappa value (κ) and percentage agreement were calculated to assess the concordance. Kappa value of < 0.2 denoted as poor agreement, between 0.2-0.4 fair agreement, between 0.4-0.6 moderate agreement, between 0.6-0.8 substantial agreement and > 0.8 almost-perfect agreement (18). G-tests, a subclass of the two-way likelihood ratio test were also used to ascertain if the proportions of isolates by one technique were different for different isolates of the other technique.

Results

Characteristics of patients and wounds

A total of 63 patients with clinico-radiological evidence of DFO, 47 male and 16 females, mean age 60.8 ± 13.5 years were included. Of these, 50 (80%) had Type 2 diabetes. The mean duration of diabetes was 16.5 ± 12.0 years and the HbA1c was $8.9\% \pm 2.2\%$. Overall, 71% had Texas 3B ulceration and the rest, 29% had Texas 3D DFU. The average duration of ulceration for the whole cohort was 13.1 ± 7.8 weeks. Chronic DFU was present in 43/63 (68%) patients. In addition, 44/63 (70%) of the cohort had received prior antibiotic therapy in the immediate past 30 days leading up to the admission with, of which 25 /44 (57%) receiving antibiotics for > 30 days. The common sites of ulceration were over the head of metatarsals 2-5 (36%), the first metatarsophalangeal joint (18%) and toes (12%). Rest (34%) had either midfoot or hindfoot ulceration; all were tracking to bone. Once admitted to hospital, the mean time difference between obtaining the deep wound swabs and surgery was 6.5 ± 4.9 days. The baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of patients are shown in

Table 1.

Number and types of bacterial pathogens isolated

Of the 63 patients, 56 (89%) patients had positive bacterial growth on DWS and 55 (87%) on SBS. The characteristics are shown in **Table 2.**

A. Deep wound swabs (DWS)

Among the DWS specimens, 24 patients had a single isolate, 8 had two isolates, 4 had three isolates and 4 had ≥ 4 isolates. In 7/63 (11%) patients, no pathogens were isolated (**Figure 1**).

The proportion of gram-positive (31/63 49%) was similar to the gram-negative isolates (38/63 60%); the proportion of anaerobic isolates (3/63 4%) was significantly lower. Among the gram positive isolates, *Staphylococcus aureus* (15/31, 50%) was the most common species; Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (3/31, 10%), *Enterococcus* (4/31, 12%) and coagulase-negative Staphylococci (8/31, 27%) were also commonly found. *Streptococcus* was noted only twice (2/31, 7%). The most common gram-negative species were *Escherichia coli* (8/38, 21%), *Proteus* spp (7/38 18%), *Klebsiella* (7/38), 18%). *Pseudomonas* spp constituted 4/38 (11% of the Gram-negative isolates). Importantly, and not included in the specific analysis above, in 16/63 (25%) patients, the DWS growth was a non-specific, uncharacterized polymicrobial growth of Gram-negative organisms and reported as such by the lab. Including such gram negative isolates, upto 75% of all the DWS specimens isolated some gram-negative organisms.

B. Surgical Bone Specimens (SBS)

For the SBS technique, 27 patients had a single isolate, 15 had two isolates, 9 had 3 isolates and there were 4 patients with ≥ 4 isolates. No growth was detected in 8/63 (13%) patients (**Figure 2**). Gram-positive organisms were noted in 33/63 patients (52%) and Gram-negative organisms in 38/63 (60%) of the patients, a proportion not dissimilar to DWS. Among the Gram-positive organisms, Coagulase-negative Staphylococci appeared as frequently (9/33, 27%) as *Staphylococcus aureus* (12/33 36%). MRSA was present in 3/33 (9%) of the isolates. Vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus* spp which was not isolated in any DWS was found in 2/33 (6%) of the SBS. Among the Gram-negative isolates, *Escherichia coli* (9/38, 24%), *Klebsiella* spp (5/38, 13%), *Proteus* spp (6/38, 16%) and *Enterobacter cloacae* (8/38, 21%) were most common; *Pseudomonas* spp was identified in 5/38 (13%) of isolates. There was a trend for a higher proportion of Gram-positive pathogens in forefoot samples (58%) when compared to a combination of midfoot and hindfoot samples (35%), however, the difference was not significant (p=0.125).

Number of pathogens reported per patient

Overall, the mean number of isolates per patient was 1.21 ± 1.0 for DWS (where reported) and 1.47 ± 1.1 for SBS ($p=0.34$). There was no difference in the number of isolates between DWS and SBS groups in those receiving prior antibiotic therapy (1.12 ± 0.98 v 1.21 ± 1.01 , $p=NS$) nor in those antibiotic naïve at admission (1.47 ± 0.99 v 1.81 ± 1.01 , $p=0.226$). However, the number of isolates on SBS was significantly lower in the group receiving prior antibiotics (1.21 ± 1.01 v 1.81 ± 1.01 , $p=0.03$)

Comparison of isolates between techniques

The isolates were strictly identical in 10/63 patients (16%). At least one isolate was identical with both techniques in 25/63 (40%) patients. The overall Kappa value for concordance between the DWS and SBS, where at least one pathogen similar specimens was fair ($\kappa= 0.302$, $p<0.0001$). The concordance for the presence of any Gram-negative isolates was moderate ($\kappa= 0.417$, $p<0.0001$). The best concordance was observed for *Staphylococcus aureus* ($\kappa=0.571$, $p<0.0001$) and *MRSA* ($\kappa=0.644$, $p<0.0001$). The concordance between specific Gram-negative isolates ranged from fair for *E.coli* ($\kappa=0.352$, $p=0.005$), *Proteus* spp ($\kappa=0.229$, $p=0.07$), to moderate for *Enterobacter* spp ($\kappa=0.412$, $p<0.0001$), but is limited by the selective identification DWS isolates. The presence of anaerobes was poorly concordant ($\kappa=0.022$, $p=0.861$). The kappa value and the chi-square likelihood ratio are presented in **Table 3**.

Clinical correlates

There was a significant correlation between DWS and SBS for the total number isolates per patient (Pearson's $r=0.419$, $p=0.005$). The total number of isolates on DWS did not correlate with gender, HbA1C, CKD status, retinopathy, ulcer duration, prior antibiotic therapy or presence of ischaemia. The total number of isolates on SBS did not correlate with gender, HbA1C, CKD status, retinopathy, ulcer duration or presence of ischaemia or duration of antibiotics. There was a correlation between number of isolates in SBS with prior antibiotic therapy of any duration ($r= -0.358$, $p=0.005$) and with the duration of ulceration ($r=0.296$, $p=0.045$).

Risk factors of negative growth in bone specimens

Given the importance of SBS in guiding targeted antibiotic therapy in DFO, factors related to negative growth were explored. Among those with negative bone growth (n=8), 3 patients had no isolates on DWS while 3 grew non-specific Gram-negative bacteria. We found that a history of prior antibiotic therapy (p=0.03) and duration of ulceration <8 weeks (p=0.025) were predictive of negative growth on SBS. Additionally, there was a trend for those who waited longer than 6 days for surgical debridement (p=0.09) and no growth on DWS (p=0.08) to have no growth on SBS.

Discussion

In our analysis of a cohort of hospitalised individuals with clinico-radiological evidence of diabetic foot osteomyelitis, we report a poor concordance between isolates obtained from deep wound swabbing *at the point of hospital admission* when compared to intra-operative bone specimens obtained at time of debridement surgery. The isolation of *S. aureus* or MRSA in a deep swab specimen was more likely to concur with presence of the same organisms on bone specimens; while the likelihood of the other isolates matching, especially Gram-negative bacilli was moderate to poor. Antecedent antibiotic therapy significantly reduced the number of isolates in surgical bone specimens compared to deep swabs. Despite this, for the two techniques, there were no major differences in the proportion Gram-positive and Gram-negative organisms isolated. While there is abundant and often conflicting literature comparing swabs and tissue samples in diabetic foot infections (3, 19, 20), there is a significant paucity of literature comparing deep swabs with intra-operative bone specimens in the context of diabetic foot infections/osteomyelitis (16, 21). To our knowledge, the present report is the largest and certainly the most focussed in terms of patient selection of a distinct clinical phenotype - *the hospitalised individual* – with diabetic foot infection and radiological suggestion of DFO.

The review of sampling methods was undertaken with a specific question in mind: in the presence of a breakthrough severe infection (limb threatening), especially those with previously recognised low-grade osteomyelitis, will a deep swab of the obviously infected ulcer and exposed bone allow the clinicians to make an early recognition of the pathogens involved? This would facilitate the introduction of targeted antibiotic therapy earlier, reducing the dependence on empirical antibiotic

therapies (21). Furthermore, and if it were the case, it would allow clinicians to confidently handle patients who decline intervention or when delays are encountered in ensuring debridement is undertaken. In contrast to most published studies, we were not specifically testing the effectiveness of the techniques *per se*. Our findings, contrary to our expectations, emphasise the perspective that pathogens involved in deep infection, may not necessarily be those represented on the surface where the milieu constantly evolves.

We found that Gram-positive isolates were represented in equal proportion to the Gram-negative isolates in bone as well as swab specimens. In previous reports (16, 22) especially those characterising isolates in swabs and tissue specimens, have suggested a higher preponderance (typically two-thirds) of Gram-positive isolates. Senneville et al, compared 69 swab and 76 bone specimens obtained through percutaneous biopsy in a group of antibiotic naive patients (for the preceding 4 weeks) with clinical and radiological characteristics of forefoot osteomyelitis (12). The precise clinical presentation of those patients was unclear although the authors clarified that most exhibited only mild to moderate infection – both important differences. They reported a higher distribution of Gram-positive pathogens (70% in bone specimens v 50% in our study) and the distribution of Gram-negative isolates was lower (18% v 60%) (12). In another study, Malone et al retrospectively analysed deep wound swabs and intra-operative bone specimens in 34 patients with predominantly Texas Grade 3B ulceration (16) but did not describe the location of the lesions (the criterion for suspected osteomyelitis being a positive probe-to-bone). They reported that 57% of the swabs and 66% of the bone specimens exhibited Gram-positive organisms; 26% of swabs and 29% of bone specimens isolated Gram-negative bacteria. In 16% of swabs and 6% of bone specimens, there was a mixed growth (16). Our centre also acts as a tertiary referral centre and the caseload consists of patients often presenting with advanced disease of long duration. The higher presence of Gram-negative organisms may thus indicate chronicity and reflect the fact that 40% of our cohort were receiving antibiotics for >4 weeks prior to admission. In our experience, this is typically co-amoxiclav, which has very good activity against Gram-positive as well as Gram organisms. Thus, our finding is in agreement with a recent report, albeit in tissue samples, from another tertiary care facility in the UK (23).

The concordance of isolates between the two techniques was only fair taking the whole group into account. However, for the presence of MSSA and gram-negatives, the κ values indicated moderate concordance and for MRSA, it was substantial. This suggests that if the isolate on DWS is MRSA or a MSSA, there is a higher likelihood that at least one the isolate will also be the same. These findings are in keeping with observations reported in the CODIFI study. However, it must be noted that the CODIFI study was undertaken in an unselected group of patients with DFI of whom only 15% were admitted to hospital and compared DWS to tissue samples only. Another study comparing isolates from bone specimens from patients having repeat surgery for recurrent osteomyelitis also reported poor concordance ($\kappa=0.180$) between bony isolates undertaken at different times in the same location (24).

One study has a number of strengths. One, we report on a group of patients belonging to a *single focussed* diabetic foot ulcer group, Texas 3 with patients either having infection (3B) or infection and ischaemia (3D). Most studies comparing microbiological sampling techniques have employed heterogeneous group of diabetic foot patients with widely variant ulcer classes and in a combination of outpatient and hospital settings (12, 23, 25). Another important strength is that our cohort is representative of real-world experience in most hospitals across the United Kingdom, and likely elsewhere. In reality, many of such diabetic foot admissions have already received outpatient antibiotic therapy, and when an exacerbation occurs, escalation to broad-spectrum antibiotics is *de rigueur* at admission. Studies focussed on the microbiological concordance between the techniques have usually excluded patients with a history of antecedent antibiotic use. While we agree such an approach is important to understand the nuances of accuracy/reliability of various techniques, it reduces the generalisation of the findings into clinical routine in the diabetic foot clinic. When faced with an episode of severe bone and soft tissue infection, microbiological evaluation after a period of antimicrobial therapy cessation is usually not an option.

The reliability (and predictive ability) of different sampling methodologies for assessment of diabetic foot infection is a subject often debated (11). DFO continues to challenge diagnostic categorisation -

clinically as well as in the laboratory (11, 26). Furthermore, within DFO, many different clinical phenotypes exist. They include DFO with early osteomyelitis and viable bone, more advanced disease involving significant bony necrosis and recurrent osteomyelitis with areas of viable as well as non-viable bone. In addition, the temporal variability of the bacterial activity and the presence of soft tissue involvement may further complicate such presentations. It is therefore difficult to capture in any one single study, the predictive ability of the tests used for diagnosis and the precise pathogen/s involved. In the presence of spreading soft tissue infection with underlying osteomyelitis, how we view discordant results needs to be debated, as it is possible that the soft tissue microbiological assessment may provide complementary information. There are no studies in DFO patients evaluating outcomes in those receiving antibiotics for bone isolates only versus those covering bone and tissue/swab isolates. Given these limitations as well as the lack of a true gold standard, we agree with the authors of the CODIFI studies, who preferred to report on 'agreement' rather than judge the results of swabs as true-positive or false-negative (11, 25). Another key clinical challenge is that most microbiology laboratories only release details of isolates that they feel are clinically relevant, whereas all isolates from bone specimens are released.

The time to surgical debridement in our cohort was nearly 6 days on average. This is considerably long, despite our practice aim debride all severely infected patients within 24 hours of admission whenever possible. Indeed, other studies comparing techniques have tried to limit the number of days between techniques to less than 3 days. Nonetheless, these figures reiterate the challenges confronted by diabetic foot teams nationally in the United Kingdom, where access to emergency theatres is limited as trauma is invariably prioritised, concerns around medical fitness for surgery and patients keen on a medical solution and hesitant to consider surgical intervention, which may involve amputation of a part of the foot. In our series, we noted a trend towards negative isolates in bone specimens among those who waited longer for their surgery. The antimicrobial management of patients with clinical DFO but with no isolates at all or positive swabs with negative bone specimens remains unclear and a serious challenge to the principles of antibiotic stewardship. While modern

molecular techniques may have a future role in situations (11, 27), expedient surgery and removal of all necrotic bone and infected soft tissue should be a priority in acute situations (26).

Our findings also have limitations. Importantly, the data presented does not include outcomes in these patients. Therefore, it is difficult to assess the impact of the results had on the choice of antibiotics and eventual clinical course. In our practice, we aim to target the organism/s noted on intra-operative bone specimens and consider targeting of deep swab/tissue isolate if the multidisciplinary team is unhappy with the trajectory of post-operative granulation. We believe future studies should report on outcomes including antibiotic choices and time to resolution of DFO and/or amputation. Another limitation is that despite severe soft tissue infection, we noted a relative paucity of anaerobic isolates reported by both the techniques. Pellizzer et al reported an anaerobic yield of 35% in swabs and 25% in paired tissue specimens of individuals admitted with limb-threatening infection. However, they only selected individuals who were not exposed to antimicrobial therapy for the preceding 3 weeks (9). The swab specimens were analysed by our microbiology laboratory using standard local protocols for processing the diabetic foot swab samples. It is possible that the isolation or reporting of anaerobes may be deficient, in particular for DWS by our current process. However, the rate of anaerobic isolates in bone was similar to other studies (12, 28). However, it is well recognised culturing anaerobes has been a challenge although concomitant use of molecular techniques may hold promise in the future (29, 30). A third limitation would be that we did not collect information on the results of any concurrent tissue or percutaneous bone specimens. This may have further enhanced our understanding but as we did not have paired specimens for most of our cohort reducing the number of comparative samples to below that is required to derive meaningful conclusions. Future studies should however consider inclusion of these techniques, which by conventional wisdom are considered more 'accurate' in comparison to DWS. This is likely to allow us to get a broader understanding of microbiological patterns in this extremely complex, controversial field.

In conclusion, our study is the first report in a defined subgroup of diabetic foot osteomyelitis and severe soft tissue infection comparing two commonly employed microbiological sampling techniques.

It suggests that deep wound swabs and intra-operative bone specimens reveal significantly discordant isolates in routine clinical practice. Additionally, in the cohort, representative of tertiary care practice, the proportion of Gram-negative isolates are similar (or higher) to Gram-positive isolates. Interpreting microbiological isolates requires close knowledge of the clinical phenotype of the diabetic foot presentation. Where necessitated, early surgical debridement should be encouraged to reduce the risk of no growth on clinically infected bone specimens. In the context of coexistent limb threatening soft-tissue infection, inclusion of clinical outcomes in future studies is necessary if we are to truly understand the impact of these findings. Otherwise, the anti-microbial management of DFO with coexistent severe soft tissue infection will remain unclear.

Table 1. Clinical characteristics of patients and diabetic foot ulcers (DFU).

Number of patients	63
Sex (M/F)	Males 47 (75%) Females 16 (25%)
Age (years)	60.79 ±13.61
Type of diabetes	Type 1 Diabetes 11 (17%) Type 2 Diabetes 52 (83%)
Duration of Diabetes (years)	16.5 ±11.97
HbA1c	72±17(mmol/mol) 8.9 ±2.15(%)
Chronic kidney disease	
	Stage 1-2 39 (62%) Stage 3 20 (32%) Stage 4/5 4 (6%)
History of Charcot arthropathy	19 (30%)
DFU classification	
	TEXAS 3B 45 (71%) TEXAS 3D 18 (29%)
DFU site	
	1 st Metatarsalphalangeal joint 11 (18%)
	Toes 8 (12%)
	Metatarsal heads 23 (36%)
	Midfoot 7 (11%)
	Hindfoot 14 (23%)
DFU aetiology	
	Purely neuropathic 45 (71%)
	Neuroischaemic 18 (29%)
Duration of DFU	
	Less than 8 weeks 33 (52%)
	Greater than 8 weeks 30 (48%)
Antibiotic treatment at point of admission	
	No antibiotics 15 (24%)
	Antibiotic of any duration 48(76%)
	Antibiotics for >4 weeks consecutively 25 (40%)

Table 2. Microbial isolates by culturing technique

Pathogens	Number of patients (% of patients)	
	Deep wound swabs	Surgical Bone Specimens
No growth	7/63 (11%)	8/63 (13%)
Total Gram-positive organisms	31/63 (49%)	33/63 (52%)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	15/31 (50%)	12/33 (36%)
Coagulase negative <i>Staphylococcus</i>	8/31 (27%)	9/33 (27%)
Methicillin Resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	5/31 (16%)	3/33(9%)
<i>Enterococcus</i> sp.	4/31(12%)	6 (18%)
Vancomycin Resistant <i>Enterococci</i>	---	4 (12%)
Specific gram-negative organisms isolated	31/63	38/63
Non-specific gram-negative isolates	16/63	0/63
Total gram-negative organisms	47/63 (75%)	38/63 (60%)
<i>Klebsiella</i> sp.	6/31 (19%)	5/38 (13%)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	7/31 (22%)	9/38 (24%)
<i>Proteus</i> spp.	6/31 (19%)	6/38 (16%)
<i>Enterobacter</i> spp.	5/31(16%)	8/38 (21%)
<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	4/31 (13%)	5/38 (13%)
<i>Morganella</i> spp.	2/31 (6.5%)	3/38 (8%)
<i>Stenotrophomonas maltophilia</i>	0	2/38 (6%)
Non-specific Gram-negative organisms	16/47 (34%)	---
Anaerobes	6/63 (10%)	4/63 (6%)

Table 3. Concordance of organism in deep wound swab and bone specimen cultures

Pathogens	Kappa value	P values	Likelihood ratio (G-test)	P value
Any Gram-positive pathogen	0.302	0.016	5.812	0.016
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	0.571	<0.0001	18.7	<0.0001
Coagulase negative Staphylococcus	0.252	0.045	3.2	0.074
Methicillin Resistant Staphylococcus aureus	0.644	<0.0001	15.8	<0.0001
Any Gram- negative Bacilli	0.417	<0.0001	11.9	<0.0001
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	0.352	0.005	5.992	0.014
Proteus spp.	0.229	0.069	2.431	0.119
Enterobacter spp.	0.471	<0.0001	9.577	0.0002
Pseudomonas spp.	0.331	0.077	2.315	0.117
Anaerobes	0.022	0.861	0.30	0.864

Figure 1: Results of bacterial culture from swab specimens

Figure 2 Results of bacterial culture from intraoperative bone specimens

Figure 3 The proportion of bacterial isolates between the specimens.

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